

FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF TRADITIONAL MEDICINE

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Abstract. *The issue of traditional medicine, its role and status are currently one of the main directions in the health care system. Recently, a particular interest in traditional medicine has begun to appear. The study of it, along with theoretical, has practical value, since it makes it possible to use the knowledge that has been formed over the centuries. In this regard, the introduction of traditional medicine is one of the tasks of modern medicine.*

Keywords: *traditional medicine, health care, theoretical and practical medicine, treatment, prevention, Tibet.*

Actuality. Over the past decade, there has been renewed attention and interest in the use of traditional medicine throughout the world. In China, traditional medicine accounts for approximately 40% of all medical care. In Chile, 71% of the population, and in Colombia, 40% of the population use such medicine. In India, 65% of the population in rural areas use Ayurveda and medicinal plants to help meet primary health care needs.

In developed countries, traditional medicine is becoming increasingly popular. For example, the proportion of the population who used such care at least once is 48% in Australia, 31% in Belgium, 70% in Canada, 49% in France and 42% in the United States. [13]

Traditional medicine is widely used to treat or prevent diseases and chronic diseases, as well as to improve quality of life.

Some evidence suggests promising potential. For example, acupuncture has been convincingly demonstrated to be effective in reducing pain and nausea and is now recognized throughout the world.

A panel of national experts from the US Institutes of Health concluded in 1997 that there is clear evidence that acupuncture treatment is more effective and has fewer side effects for some symptoms than conventional treatments. In Germany and the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, 70% and 90%, respectively, of pain management clinics use acupuncture.

Traditional medicine is also used in the treatment and care of life-threatening diseases such as malaria and AIDS. In Ghana, Mali, Nigeria and Zambia, treatment with herbal remedies is the first-line treatment for more than 60% of children with fever. Studies in Africa and North America have shown that up to 75% of people with HIV/AIDS use traditional medicine alone or in combination with other medicines for various symptoms or conditions. Over the past two decades, interest in traditional systems of medicine, especially herbal medicines, has grown significantly in both developed and developing countries.

The use of herbal preparations by the world's population is increasing every day in order to be closer to nature and avoid the negative effects of synthetic drugs. According to WHO (2011), almost 80% of the world's population uses mainly herbal preparations within the primary health care organization.

According to the results of a public opinion research center in Germany, more than 50% of respondents prefer to be treated with drugs of natural origin, and only 20% believe that synthetic substances are more reliable.

[12] The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD–3968 dated October 12, 2018 “On measures to streamline the sphere of traditional medicine in the Republic of Uzbekistan” stipulates that the large-scale reforms in the healthcare system carried out in recent years have contributed to expanding citizens’ access to modern medical services, medicines, as well as improving the quality and effectiveness of medical care provided.

Traditional medicine plays an important place in the treatment of acute and complex diseases, and the services of traditional healers have become widely in demand among various segments of the population. [1] In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD No. 4668 dated 10.04. 2020 “On additional measures for the development of traditional medicine in the Republic of Uzbekistan” refers to the Concept for the development of the healthcare system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019–2025 and the Concept for the prevention of non-communicable diseases and support for a healthy lifestyle and increasing the level of physical activity of the population for 2019–2022, measures are being implemented aimed at ensuring the efficiency, quality and accessibility of medical care, the introduction of modern achievements of medical science and technology, and the formation of a healthy lifestyle of the population. [2]

Traditional medicine, the quality, safety and effectiveness of which has been proven in practice, occupies an important place in ensuring public health, providing health care, preventing and treating various diseases, especially chronic ones. Over the past period of time, as a result of the measures taken, a legal framework has been formed in the field of provision of services by traditional healers, the Association of Traditional Medicine of Uzbekistan and priority conditions for the effective and safe use of methods and achievements of traditional medicine have been created, the main goals and directions of its development have been determined. At the same time, the analysis of the work carried out indicates the need to further improve the provision of traditional medicine services, mechanisms for assessing the effectiveness of its methods, consistent integration of traditional medicine into the modern healthcare system, and advanced training of specialists and other medical workers in this area in order to accelerate the integration of effective methods of prevention, diagnosis and treatment of diseases through traditional medicine into the practice of modern medicine, further strengthening the health of citizens, establishing a system of training, retraining and advanced training of specialists, as well as conducting research work in this area.

The World Health Organization is implementing the Traditional Medicine Strategy 2014–2023, which aims to support Member States in: harnessing the potential contribution of traditional medicine to health, well-being, people-centred health care, improving the quality of health care services, expanding universal health coverage, creating opportunities for consumers to make informed choices in caring for their health, appropriately promoting the safe and effective use of traditional medicine by establishing norms and regulations, conducting research and integrating traditional medicine products and practices into the health system, upgrading human resources, improving skills, services and treatments. Traditional medicine includes practical experience in methods and means of diagnosis and treatment, accumulated over centuries in different countries and passed on from generation to generation. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines traditional medicine as including various health-related approaches, knowledge and beliefs, as well

as medicines of plant, animal and/or mineral origin, spiritual therapy, manual therapy and exercises, used alone or in combination to support well-being, as well as the treatment, diagnosis and prevention of disease.[11] Traditional medicine is also commonly defined by other terms - traditional, alternative, natural, unorthodox or complementary medicine. Traditional medicine, existing in oral tradition and tied to a specific geographical region, is usually passed on from teacher to student. Traditional medicine has been preserved and developed in written monuments, with formulated concepts that differ from the theories of modern scientific medicine. The term "traditional medicine" is a comprehensive term that refers to systems of medicine, such as traditional Chinese medicine, Indian medicine and Arabic Unani medicine, for example, as well as various forms of indigenous medicine. The terms "complementary medicine" and "alternative medicine" are used interchangeably with "traditional medicine" in some countries.

Conclusions. Traditional medicine is the sum total of the accumulated knowledge, beliefs and skills based on the theories, beliefs and experiences of indigenous peoples and representatives of various cultures, whether we can explain them or not, which are used for maintaining health, as well as for prevention, diagnosis and improvement in physical and mental disorders. Many traditional medicine methods are not accepted in traditional medicine. Even scientific research cannot always explain the phenomenon of abilities and the effectiveness of healing techniques of healers. However, modern medicine does not dispute the right to the existence of such an alternative to its own technological and scientifically based methods. The main thing is that they do not harm patients. Today, in the field of international medical tourism, there is greater demand for medical and health programs used for rehabilitation and restoration of the body, which are carried out according to folk oriental methods. They are also applicable for the general strengthening of human immunity.

Conventionally, non-traditional methods of treatment are divided into alternative and complementary. Alternative therapy involves a complete rejection of standard therapy, and complementary therapy is used in combination with standard treatment methods. Today, traditional and alternative medicine is increasingly being included in the programs of even ordinary medical institutions and centers for the improvement and rehabilitation of the human body, especially in the countries of Asia and Latin America.

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